

Design Summaries of Steel Moment Resisting Frames with Elastic and Dissipative Panel Zones

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In this report, thirty-two (32) archetype steel office building designs are summarized. The designs are based on (AISC 2016a; b; c; ASCE 2016). A soil class D and risk category II are assumed. The design location is urban California, and specifically Los Angeles, with (Latitude = 33.996° and Longitude = -118.162°). The steel buildings comprise of two perimeter steel MRFs, two orthogonal concentrically braced frames, and a gravity frame system, as depicted in the plan view in **Figure 1**. Four-, Eight-, 12- and 20-storey steel buildings are considered. The typical story height is 4m in all examined cases. The first story height is 4.3m for the four-story steel MRF. The rest of the steel MRFs have a first story height of 4.2m. The elevation views of all MRFs are shown in Figure 2 (four-story), Figure 3 (eight-story), Figure 4 (twelve-story), and Figure 5 (twenty-story). Beams and columns are made of A992, Gr. 50 (i.e., nominal yield stress, $f_y = 345\text{MPa}$) with a 100mm thick slab that rests on a 90mm thick steel deck. Pre-qualified WUF-W beam-to-column connections are considered.

The beam-to-column web panel zones are designed with the following targeted panel zone distortions, $\gamma_d = [1, 4, 10, 15] \cdot \gamma_y$, where γ_y is the panel zone shear distortions at yield. The last two values do not comply with AISC 360-16. The panel zone shear resistance, R_n (AISC 2016c), over the panel zone shear demand, R_u (AISC 2016b), values are reported in **Table 1** for all the designs. Column splices are positioned at the mid-height of every other story. The MRFs are designed with a response modification coefficient, $R = 8$, an overstrength factor, $\Omega_0 = 3$ and a deflection amplification factor, $C_d = 5.5$. In **Tables 2-9**, the cross-sections of the beams and the columns and the doubler plate thicknesses are shown for all the steel MRF designs.

The seismic performance of the above-mentioned steel MRFs has been thoroughly investigated by the authors through nonlinear static and dynamic analyses (Skiadopoulos and Lignos 2022).

Figure 1. Plan view of the three- and five-bar steel MRFs.

The MRFs are designed by considering:

- P-delta effects by leaning column modelling.
- The panel zone contribution to the MRF deformations.
- End beam offsets (physical dimensions of beams and columns).
- Response spectrum analysis (RSA) instead of equivalent lateral force (ELF) method.
- Wind design is neglected as discussed in prior studies (Elkady 2016; NIST 2010).

The loads for which the MRFs are designed are the following:

- Dead load: $4.3kN/m^2$ (90psf)
- Live load floor: $2.4kN/m^2$ (50psf)
- Dead load roof: $0.96kN/m^2$ (20psf)
- Cladding: $1.2kN/m^2$ (25psf)
- Earthquake load: design spectrum as shown in **Figure 6**.

Figure 2. Elevation view of the four-storey steel MRFs: (a) three-bay; and (b) five-bay.

Figure 3. Elevation view of the eight-storey steel MRFs: (a) three-bay; and (b) five-bay.

Figure 4. Elevation view of the twelve-storey steel MRFs: (a) three-bay; and (b) five-bay.

Figure 5. Elevation view of the twenty-storey steel MRFs: (a) three-bay; and (b) five-bay.

Figure 6. Design spectrum and archetype MRF periods.

Table 1. Archetype steel MRF panel zone shear resistance over panel zone shear demand values and first mode periods.

		γ_d	R_n/R_u	T_1 (s)
4-story	3-bay	γ_y	1.25	1.28
		$4\gamma_y$	1.03	1.29
		$10\gamma_y$	0.82	1.31
		$15\gamma_y$	0.79	1.32
		γ_y	1.26	1.28
4-story	5-bay	$4\gamma_y$	1.04	1.29
		$10\gamma_y$	0.85	1.31
		$15\gamma_y$	0.75	1.32
		γ_y	1.22	2.04
		8-story	3-bay	$4\gamma_y$
$10\gamma_y$	0.85			2.11
$15\gamma_y$	0.77			2.13
γ_y	1.23			2.06
8-story	5-bay			$4\gamma_y$
		$10\gamma_y$	0.84	2.12
		$15\gamma_y$	0.74	2.14
		γ_y	1.23	2.41
		12-story	3-bay	$4\gamma_y$
$10\gamma_y$	0.81			2.49
$15\gamma_y$	0.75			2.50
γ_y	1.21			2.47
12-story	5-bay			$4\gamma_y$
		$10\gamma_y$	0.84	2.55
		$15\gamma_y$	0.76	2.57
		γ_y	1.24	3.91
		20-story	3-bay	$4\gamma_y$
$10\gamma_y$	0.83			3.98
$15\gamma_y$	0.74			4.00
γ_y	1.23			3.86
20-story	5-bay			$4\gamma_y$
		$10\gamma_y$	0.85	3.94
		$15\gamma_y$	0.75	3.97

Table 2. Four-storey, three-bay steel MRF design.

Story/Floor	Columns		Doubler plates (in)				Beam
	Exterior	Interior	$\gamma_d = \gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 4\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 10\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 15\gamma_y$	
4/Roof	W24x76	W24x84	4/16, 14/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 6/16	W18x60
3/4	W24x103, W24x76	W24x146, W24x84	4/16, 14/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 6/16	W18x60
2/3	W24x103	W24x146	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W24x76
1/2	W24x103	W24x146	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W24x76

Table 3. Four-storey, five-bay steel MRF design.

Story/Floor	Columns		Doubler plates (in)				Beam
	Exterior	Interior	$\gamma_d = \gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 4\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 10\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 15\gamma_y$	
4/Roof	W21x50	W21x62	2/16, 10/16	1/16, 7/16	0, 5/16	0, 3/16	W18x40
3/4	W21x83, W21x50	W21x111, W21x62	2/16, 10/16	1/16, 7/16	0, 5/16	0, 3/16	W18x40
2/3	W21x83	W21x111	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W21x62
1/2	W21x83	W21x111	4/16, 16/16	2/16, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W21x62

Table 4. Eight-storey, three-bay MRF design.

Story/Floor	Columns		Doubler plates (in)				Beam
	Exterior	Interior	$\gamma_d = \gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 4\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 10\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 15\gamma_y$	
8/Roof	W24x94	W24x94	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W21x68
7/8	W24x103, W24x94	W24x131, W24x94	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W21x68
6/7	W24x103	W24x131	4/16, 16/16	2/16, 11/16	0, 7/16	0, 6/16	W24x76
5/6	W24x131, W24x103	W24x176, W24x131	4/16, 16/16	2/16, 11/16	0, 7/16	0, 6/16	W24x76
4/5	W24x131	W24x176	6/16, 18/16	3/16, 12/16	1/16, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x94
3/4	W24x162, W24x131	W24x192, W24x176	6/16, 18/16	3/16, 12/16	1/16, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x94
2/3	W24x162	W24x192	5/16, 20/16	2/16, 13/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x102
1/2	W24x162	W24x192	5/16, 20/16	2/16, 13/16	0, 10/16	0, 7/16	W27x102

Table 5. Eight-storey, five-bay MRF design.

Story/Floor	Columns		Doubler plates (in)				Beam
	Exterior	Interior	$\gamma_d = \gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 4\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 10\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 15\gamma_y$	
8/Roof	W24x62	W24x84	3/16, 12/16	1/16, 9/16	0, 6/16	0, 4/16	W18x55
7/8	W24x84, W24x62	W24x94, W24x84	3/16, 12/16	1/16, 9/16	0, 6/16	0, 4/16	W18x55
6/7	W24x84	W24x94	3/16, 13/16	1/16, 9/16	0, 6/16	0, 5/16	W21x62
5/6	W24x103, W24x84	W24x103, W24x94	3/16, 13/16	1/16, 9/16	0, 6/16	0, 5/16	W21x62
4/5	W24x103	W24x103	4/16, 16/16	1/16, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W21x73
3/4	W24x131, W24x103	W24x131, W24x103	4/16, 16/16	1/16, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W21x73
2/3	W24x131	W24x131	3/16, 16/16	1/16, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W24x76
1/2	W24x131	W24x131	3/16, 16/16	1/16, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W24x76

Table 6. Twelve-storey, three-bay MRF design.

Story/Floor	Columns		Doubler plates (in)				Beam
	Exterior	Interior	$\gamma_d = \gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 4\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 10\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 15\gamma_y$	
12/Roof	W27x94	W27x102	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W24x76
11/12	W27x114, W27x94	W27x129, W27x102	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W24x76
10/11	W27x114	W27x129	5/16, 17/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x94
9/10	W27x129, W27x114	W27x194, W27x129	5/16, 17/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x94
8/9	W27x129	W27x194	5/16, 17/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W30x108
7/8	W27x178, W27x129	W27x217, W27x194	5/16, 17/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W30x108
6/7	W27x178	W27x217	6/16, 21/16	2/16, 14/16	0, 10/16	0, 8/16	W30x124
5/6	W27x217, W27x178	W27x258, W27x217	6/16, 21/16	2/16, 14/16	0, 10/16	0, 8/16	W30x124
4/5	W27x217	W27x258	5/16, 21/16	1/16, 13/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W30x132
3/4	W27x235, W27x217	W27x281, W27x258	5/16, 21/16	1/16, 13/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W30x132
2/3	W27x235	W27x281	4/16, 18/16	0, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 5/16	W30x132
1/2	W27x235	W27x281	4/16, 19/16	0, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W30x132

Table 7. Twelve-storey, five-bay MRF design.

Story/Floor	Columns		Doubler plates (in)				Beam
	Exterior	Interior	$\gamma_d = \gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 4\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 10\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 15\gamma_y$	
12/Roof	W24x84	W24x84	4/16, 20/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 6/16	W18x60
11/12	W24x94, W24x84	W24x94, W24x84	4/16, 20/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 6/16	W18x60
10/11	W24x94	W24x94	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W21x68
9/10	W24x103, W24x94	W24x131, W24x94	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W21x68
8/9	W24x103	W24x131	4/16, 16/16	2/16, 11/16	0, 7/16	0, 6/16	W24x76
7/8	W24x131, W24x103	W24x146, W24x131	4/16, 16/16	2/16, 11/16	0, 7/16	0, 6/16	W24x76
6/7	W24x131	W24x146	6/16, 20/16	3/16, 14/16	1/16, 10/16	0, 8/16	W27x94
5/6	W24x146, W24x131	W24x176, W24x146	6/16, 20/16	3/16, 14/16	1/16, 10/16	0, 8/16	W27x94
4/5	W24x146	W24x176	5/16, 18/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x94
3/4	W24x162, W24x146	W24x192, W24x176	5/16, 18/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x94
2/3	W24x162	W24x192	5/16, 20/16	2/16, 13/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x102
1/2	W24x162	W24x192	5/16, 20/16	2/16, 13/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x102

Table 8. Twenty-storey, three-bay MRF design.

Story/Floor	Columns		Doubler plates (in)				Beam
	Exterior	Interior	$\gamma_d = \gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 4\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 10\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 15\gamma_y$	
20/Roof	W33x130	W36x150	5/16, 15/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W27x114
19/20	W33x152, W33x130	W36x170, W36x150	5/16, 15/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W27x114
18/19	W33x152	W36x170	5/16, 17/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W30x132
17/18	W33x169, W33x152	W36x194, W36x170	5/16, 17/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W30x132
16/17	W33x169	W36x194	5/16, 16/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 4/16	W30x132
15/16	W33x201, W33x169	W36x262, W36x194	5/16, 16/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 4/16	W30x132
14/15	W33x201	W36x262	6/16, 18/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 5/16	W33x152
13/14	W33x241, W33x201	W36x282, W36x262	6/16, 18/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 5/16	W33x152
12/13	W33x241	W36x282	4/16, 17/16	1/16, 11/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W36x160
11/12	W33x291, W33x241	W36x302, W36x282	4/16, 17/16	1/16, 11/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W36x160
10/11	W33x291	W36x302	2/16, 16/16	0, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 4/16	W36x160
9/10	W33x318, W33x291	W36x330, W36x302	2/16, 16/16	0, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 4/16	W36x160
8/9	W33x318	W36x330	0, 15/16	0, 9/16	0, 5/16	0, 3/16	W36x160
7/8	W33x387, W33x318	W36x330	0, 15/16	0, 9/16	0, 5/16	0, 3/16	W36x160
6/7	W33x387	W36x330	0, 17/16	0, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 4/16	W36x170
5/6	W36x441, W33x387	W36x361, W36x330	0, 17/16	0, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 4/16	W36x170
4/5	W36x441	W36x361	0, 15/16	0, 8/16	0, 5/16	0, 3/16	W36x170
3/4	W36x487, W36x441	W36x395, W36x361	0, 15/16	0, 8/16	0, 5/16	0, 3/16	W36x170
2/3	W36x487	W36x395	0, 13/16	0, 7/16	0, 3/16	0, 1/16	W36x170
1/2	W36x487	W36x395	0, 13/16	0, 7/16	0, 3/16	0, 1/16	W36x170

Table 9. Twenty-storey, five-bay MRF design.

Story/Floor	Columns		Doubler plates (in)				Beam
	Exterior	Interior	$\gamma_d = \gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 4\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 10\gamma_y$	$\gamma_d = 15\gamma_y$	
20/Roof	W27x94	W27x102	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W24x76
19/20	W27x114, W27x94	W27x129, W27x102	4/16, 15/16	2/16, 10/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W24x76
18/19	W27x114	W27x129	5/16, 17/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x94
17/18	W27x129, W27x114	W27x161, W27x129	5/16, 17/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 9/16	0, 7/16	W27x94
16/17	W27x129	W27x161	4/16, 17/16	1/16, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W27x94
15/16	W27x161, W27x129	W27x194, W27x161	4/16, 17/16	1/16, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W27x94
14/15	W27x161	W27x194	5/16, 17/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W30x108
13/14	W27x178, W27x161	W27x217, W27x194	5/16, 17/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 8/16	0, 6/16	W30x108
12/13	W27x178	W27x217	6/16, 21/16	2/16, 14/16	0, 10/16	0, 8/16	W30x124
11/12	W27x194, W27x178	W27x235, W27x217	6/16, 21/16	2/16, 14/16	0, 10/16	0, 8/16	W30x124
10/11	W27x194	W27x235	5/16, 19/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 9/16	0, 6/16	W30x124
9/10	W27x217, W27x194	W27x258, W27x235	5/16, 19/16	2/16, 12/16	0, 9/16	0, 6/16	W30x124
8/9	W27x217	W27x258	4/16, 18/16	0, 11/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W30x124
7/8	W27x235, W27x217	W27x281, W27x258	4/16, 18/16	0, 11/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W30x124
6/7	W27x235	W27x281	4/16, 18/16	0, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 5/16	W30x132
5/6	W27x281, W27x235	W27x307, W27x281	4/16, 18/16	0, 11/16	0, 8/16	0, 5/16	W30x132
4/5	W27x281	W27x307	1/16, 17/16	0, 10/16	0, 6/16	0, 4/16	W30x132
3/4	W27x307, W27x281	W27x336, W27x307	1/16, 17/16	0, 10/16	0, 6/16	0, 4/16	W30x132
2/3	W27x307	W27x336	2/16, 19/16	0, 12/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W30x148
1/2	W27x307	W27x336	2/16, 19/16	0, 12/16	0, 7/16	0, 5/16	W30x148

The above designs were controlled by the drift limit as per ASCE (2016), while all beam and column strength checks are respected. The drift check was performed for the $\gamma_d = 15\gamma_y$ cases, since deformations are higher in these cases. The drift stability coefficient checks are shown in **Figure 7** and **Figure 8**.

Figure 7. Drift and stability coefficient check for the four-, eight-, twelve- and twenty-storey, three-bay MRFs.

Figure 8. Drift and stability coefficient check for the four-, eight-, twelve- and twenty-storey, five-bay MRFs.

The strong column weak beam (SCWB) check for all MRFs is respected and shown in **Tables 10-17**.

Table 10. SCWB ratio for the four-storey, three-bay MRF

Story/Floor	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4
4/Roof	1.2	0.7	0.7	1.2
3/4	2.2	1.4	1.4	2.2
2/3	1.8	1.7	1.7	1.8
1/2	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.5

Table 11. SCWB ratio for the four-storey, five-bay MRF

Story/Floor	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5	Column 6
4/Roof	1.1	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	1.1
3/4	2.0	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	2.0
2/3	1.9	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.9
1/2	1.6	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.6

Table 12. SCWB ratio for the eight-storey, three-bay MRF

Story/Floor	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4
8/Roof	1.2	0.6	0.6	1.2
7/8	2.3	1.2	1.2	2.3
6/7	1.9	1.5	1.5	1.9
5/6	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.6
4/5	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.5
3/4	1.2	1.4	1.4	1.2
2/3	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4
1/2	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.2

Table 13. SCWB ratio for the eight-storey, five-bay MRF

Story/Floor	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5	Column 6
8/Roof	1.0	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	1.0
7/8	2.0	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	2.0
6/7	2.2	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	2.2
5/6	1.9	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.9
4/5	1.9	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.9
3/4	1.7	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.7
2/3	1.9	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.9
1/2	1.7	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.7

Table 14. SCWB ratio for the twelve-storey, three-bay MRF

Story/Floor	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4
12/Roof	1.1	0.6	0.6	1.1
11/12	2.1	1.2	1.2	2.1
10/11	1.7	1.1	1.1	1.7
9/10	1.5	1.1	1.1	1.5
8/9	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.3
7/8	1.1	1.4	1.4	1.1
6/7	1.5	1.3	1.3	1.5
5/6	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.3
4/5	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.6
3/4	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.3
2/3	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.4
1/2	1.2	1.5	1.5	1.2

Table 15. SCWB ratio for the twelve-storey, five-bay MRF

Story/Floor	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5	Column 6
12/Roof	1.4	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7	1.4
11/12	2.7	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	2.7
10/11	2.3	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	2.3
9/10	2.1	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.1	2.1
8/9	1.7	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.7
7/8	1.6	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.6
6/7	1.5	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.5
5/6	1.4	1.0	1.1	1.1	1.0	1.4
4/5	1.5	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.5
3/4	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.3
2/3	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.3
1/2	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.1

Table 16. SCWB ratio for the twenty-storey, three-bay MRF

Story/Floor	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4
20/Roof	1.1	0.7	0.7	1.1
19/20	2.1	1.3	1.3	2.1
18/19	1.8	1.2	1.2	1.8
17/18	1.7	1.1	1.1	1.7
16/17	1.7	1.3	1.3	1.7
15/16	1.5	1.2	1.2	1.5
14/15	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4
13/14	1.2	1.4	1.4	1.2
12/13	1.4	1.3	1.3	1.4
11/12	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.2
10/11	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.6
9/10	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3
8/9	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4
7/8	1.2	1.4	1.4	1.2
6/7	1.6	1.3	1.3	1.6
5/6	1.4	1.3	1.3	1.4
4/5	1.8	1.4	1.4	1.8
3/4	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.5
2/3	1.7	1.6	1.6	1.7
1/2	1.4	1.6	1.6	1.4

Table 17. SCWB ratio for the twenty-storey, five-bay MRF

Story/Floor	Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5	Column 6
20/Roof	1.1	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	1.1
19/20	2.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	2.2
18/19	1.8	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.8
17/18	1.7	1.0	1.1	1.1	1.0	1.7
16/17	1.9	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.9
15/16	1.7	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.7
14/15	1.8	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.8
13/14	1.7	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.7
12/13	1.5	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.5
11/12	1.4	1.1	1.3	1.3	1.1	1.4
10/11	1.5	1.2	1.4	1.4	1.2	1.5
9/10	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.3
8/9	1.5	1.3	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.5
7/8	1.3	1.3	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.3
6/7	1.3	1.3	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.3
5/6	1.1	1.3	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.1
4/5	1.5	1.4	1.6	1.6	1.4	1.5
3/4	1.3	1.4	1.6	1.6	1.4	1.3
2/3	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.6	1.4	1.2
1/2	1.1	1.3	1.5	1.5	1.3	1.1

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